

Scoping Document

Deliverable D8.1 |
Dissemination level: PU

Document information

Deliverable Title/Number	D8.1 - Scoping Document
Description	Definition of the exact scope for the harmonization process
Lead beneficiary	TUB
Lead Authors	Hannah Welsh, Matthias Finkbeiner [TUB]
Contributors	UGENT, RISE, J&J, SADG, AZ, BIP KG, SOF, NOVO, GSK, UCB BE, MSERO, MKDG, PFE-INC, PFE-IT, PFE-LIM, PFE-RDUK, PFE-IRL, UCB NL, SERVIER, ABBV-DE
Contractual delivery date:	31/10/2025
Actual delivery date:	31/10/2025
Dissemination level	PUBLIC

Document Approval

Name	Organisation	Role	Action	Date
Bert Verstappen	Johnson & Johnson	WP 8 co-lead	Approved	17/10/2025
Kranti Navare		WP 8 member		
Ad Ragas	Radboud University	WP 7 member	Approved	29/10/2025
Rosalie van Zelm				
Fabienne Brutin	Benkei	Executive Committee	Approved	27/10/2025
Christian Schönau	Sanofi			
Sarah Costers	Ghent University			
PHARMECO Steering team			Approved	31/10/2025

Document History

Version	Date	Modifications	Authors
V0	25/06/2025	Template	BENKEI
V1	02/07/2025	Populating template with results of the scoping workshops	TUB
V2	14/07/2025	Integrated comments from RISE and UGENT	TUB

V3	22/07/2025	Integrating feedback from co-leads (TUB, J&J, SADG); Version for WP8 commenting phase	TUB
V4	24/09/2025	Integrated changes based on input from WP partners during commenting phase	TUB
V5	06/10/2025	Input from WP partners in final scoping meeting integrated	TUB
V6	30/10/2025	Corrections from peer review integrated and approved.	TUB
VF	31/10/2025	Final version	TUB

To request a change to this document, contact the Document Author.

Configuration Management

Nature of Deliverable		
R	Document, report (excluding the periodic and final reports)	x
DEC	Websites, patents filing, press & media actions, videos, etc.	
DEM	Demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs	
OTHER	Software, technical diagram, algorithms, models, etc.	
ETHICS	Deliverables related to ethics issues.	
DATA	Data sets, microdata, etc	
DMP	Data management plan	
Dissemination level		
PU	Public, fully open, e.g., web (Deliverables flagged as public will be automatically published in CORDIS projects.)	x
SEN	Sensitive, limited under the conditions of the Grant Agreement	

Glossary

Acronym/abbreviations	
API	Active pharmaceutical ingredient
ATC	Anatomical Therapeutic Chemical classification scheme
cEF	Complete E Factor
CIP	Cleaning in place
DP	Drug product
DS	Drug substance
EoL	End-of-life
FU	Functional unit
GHG	Greenhouse gas
iGAL	Innovation Green Aspiration Level
LCA	Life cycle assessment
LCI	Life cycle inventory
LCIA	Life cycle impact assessment
PCF	Product carbon footprint
PCR	Product category rules
PMI	Process mass intensity
R&D	Research and development
SIP	Sterilisation in place

Glossary	
Allocation	Partitioning the input or output flows of a process or a product system between the product system under study and one or more other product systems (ISO 14040:2006, definition 3.17) (International Organization for Standardization, 2006a)
Active pharmaceutical ingredient	Any substance or mixture of substances intended to be used in the manufacture of a drug (medicinal) product and that, when used in the production of a drug, becomes an active ingredient of the drug product (European Medicines Agency, 2000)
Active substance	Any substance or mixture of substances intended to be used in the manufacture of a medicinal product and that, when used in its production, becomes an active ingredient of that product intended to exert a pharmacological, immunological or metabolic action with a view to restoring, correcting or modifying physiological functions or to make a medical diagnosis. (European Commission, 2023a, p. 48)
Biologic	Active substance which is derived from a biological source (European Commission, 2023a). They are usually manufactured in living systems, such as microorganisms or cells in complex manufacturing processes (European Commission, 2013a, p. 8)
Comparative assertion	Environmental claim regarding the superiority or equivalence of one product versus a competing product that performs the same function

	(ISO 14040:2006, definition 3.6) (International Organization for Standardization, 2006a)
Cradle to gate	A partial product supply chain, from the extraction of raw materials (cradle) up to the manufacturer's "gate". The distribution, storage, use stage and end-of-life stages of the supply chain are omitted. (European Commission, 2013b, p. 58)
Cradle to grave	A product's life cycle that includes raw material extraction, processing, distribution, storage, use, and disposal or recycling stages. All relevant inputs and outputs are considered for all of the stages of the life cycle. (European Commission, 2013b, p. 58)
Declared unit	Quantity of a product for use as a reference unit in a Type III environmental declaration or footprint communication, based on one or more information modules (which are unit processes or combination of unit processes forming part of a product life cycle) Note: The declared unit is used where the function and the reference scenario for the whole life cycle cannot be stated. (ISO/TS 14027:2017, definition 3.10) (International Organization for Standardization, 2017)
Dosage form	The form of the completed pharmaceutical product, e.g. tablet, capsule, injection, elixir, suppository. (European Medicines Agency, 2025a)
Drug product	The final dosage form of a pharmaceutical product, including drug substance and excipients.
Drug substance	Synonymous to active pharmaceutical ingredient. (European Medicines Agency, 2000)
Environment	Surroundings in which an organisation operates, including air, water, land, natural resources, flora, fauna, humans, and their interrelation (ISO 14001:2015, definition 3.2.1) (International Organization for Standardization, 2015)
Environmental aspect	Element of an organization's activities, products or services that interacts or can interact with the environment (ISO 14001:2015, definition 3.2.6) (International Organization for Standardization, 2015)
Environmental impact	Change to the environment, whether adverse or beneficial, wholly or partially resulting from an organization's environmental aspects (ISO 14001:2015, definition 3.2.4) (International Organization for Standardization, 2015)
Environmental performance	Performance (measurable result) related to the management of environmental aspects (ISO 14001:2015, definition 3.4.11) (International Organization for Standardization, 2015)
Excipient	A constituent of a medicine other than the active substance. (European Medicines Agency, 2025b)
Functional unit	Quantified performance of a product system for use as a reference unit (ISO 14001:2004, definition 3.20) (International Organization for Standardization, 2015)
Gate to gate	A partial product's supply chain that includes only the processes carried out on a product within a specific organisation or site. (European Commission, 2013b, p. 59)
Gate to grave	A partial product's supply chain that includes only the distribution, storage, use, and disposal or recycling stages. (European Commission, 2013b, p. 59)

Impact category	Class representing environmental issues of concern to which life cycle inventory analysis results may be assigned (ISO 14040:2006, definition 3.39) (International Organization for Standardization, 2006a)
Impact category indicator	Quantifiable representation of an impact category (ISO 14040:2006, definition 3.40) (International Organization for Standardization, 2006a)
Life cycle	Consecutive and interlinked stages of a product system, from raw material acquisition or generation from natural resources to final disposal (ISO 14040:2006, definition 3.1) (International Organization for Standardization, 2006a)
Life cycle assessment	Compilation and evaluation of the inputs, outputs and the potential environmental impacts of a product system throughout its life cycle (ISO 14040:2006, definition 3.2) (International Organization for Standardization, 2006a)
Life cycle impact assessment	Phase of life cycle assessment aimed at understanding and evaluating the magnitude and significance of the potential environmental impacts for a product system throughout the life cycle of the product (ISO 14040:2006, definition 3.4) (International Organization for Standardization, 2006a)
Life cycle inventory analysis	Phase of life cycle assessment involving the compilation and quantification of inputs and outputs for a product throughout its life cycle (ISO 14040:2006, definition 3.3). The outcome of the life cycle inventory analysis ... catalogues the flows crossing the system boundary and provides the starting point for life cycle impact assessment (ISO 14040:2006, definition 3.24) (International Organization for Standardization, 2006a)
Process	Set of interrelated or interacting activities that transforms inputs into outputs (ISO 14001:2015, definition 3.3.5) (International Organization for Standardization, 2015)
Product	Any goods or service (ISO 14040:2006, definition 3.9, without notes) (International Organization for Standardization, 2006a)
Product carbon footprint	Sum of greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions and (GHG) removals in a product system, expressed as CO ₂ equivalents and based on a life cycle assessment using the single impact category of climate change (ISO14067:2018, definition 3.1.1.1) (International Organization for Standardization, 2018)
Product category rules	Set of specific rules, requirements and guidelines for developing Type III environmental declarations and footprint communications for one or more product categories (ISO 14067:2018, definition 3.1.1.9) (International Organization for Standardization, 2018)
Product system	Collection of unit processes with elementary and product flows, performing one or more defined functions, and which models the life cycle of a product (ISO 14040:2006, definition 3.28) (International Organization for Standardization, 2006a)
Radiopharmaceutical	Any medicinal product that, when ready for use, contains one or more radionuclides (radioactive isotopes) included for a medicinal purpose (European Commission, 2023a, p. 49)
Raw material	Primary or secondary material that is used to produce a product (ISO 14040:2006, definition 3.15, without notes) (International Organization for Standardization, 2006a)

Reference flow	Measure of the outputs from processes in a given product system required to fulfil the function expressed by the functional unit (ISO 14040:2006, definition 3.29) (International Organization for Standardization, 2006a)
Synthetics	Used here synonymously to ‘small molecules’; Active pharmaceutical ingredients manufactured typically by chemical synthesis as opposed to being produced in living systems (European Commission, 2013a, p. 8)
System boundary	Set of criteria specifying which unit processes are part of a product system (ISO 14040:2006, definition 3.32) (International Organization for Standardization, 2006a)

Disclaimer

The PHARMECO project is supported by the Innovative Health Initiative Joint Undertaking (IHI JU) under grant agreement No 101165889. The JU receives support from the European Union’s Horizon Europe research and innovation programme and COCIR, EFPIA, Europa Bío, MedTech Europe, and Vaccines Europe. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or IHI JU. Neither the European Union nor IHI JU can be held responsible for them.

Proprietary Rights Statement

This document contains information, which is proprietary to the PHARMECO Consortium. Neither this document nor the information contained herein shall be used, duplicated or communicated by any means to any third party, in whole or in parts, except with prior written consent of the PHARMECO consortium.

Reproduction

Reproduction is authorised provided the source is acknowledged.

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

In PHARMECO, work package 8 (WP8) aims to facilitate the harmonisation process and establish a harmonised guideline for the environmental sustainability assessment of (bio)pharmaceuticals. The guideline and its dissemination are the ultimate deliverables of the work package. This will be carried out by bringing relevant public and industry stakeholders together in a consensus-based harmonisation process, consisting of several rounds of discussions and workshops over five years. The methodological decisions will undergo road-testing using case studies within the project, to ensure applicability and robustness of the guideline.

Life cycle assessment (LCA) is a standardised method (ISO 14040/44:2006) that enables the systematic analysis of the potential environmental impacts occurring throughout a product's life cycle (International Organization for Standardization, 2006b) and has become a widely used method to assess the environmental impact of both products and processes in the pharmaceutical industry (Satta et al., 2024).

Although several initiatives have published method documents, guidelines and standards to implement LCA in the pharmaceutical and healthcare sectors, a preliminary analysis of existing method documents by PHARMECO WP8 has shown that there remain key aspects that still lack harmonisation, such as the product scope, chosen impacts and impact categories, consideration of health care pathways, functional unit, and handling of data gaps. Furthermore, most standards and guidelines to date are communication focused.

Based on the initial analysis of the method documents, a series of three scoping workshops was held with the public and industry partners of WP8 to define the scope of methodological harmonisation to be conducted within PHARMECO and of the resulting LCA guideline. Scoping decisions were documented in the form of meeting minutes.

As a result of the scoping workshops, the WP elected to follow a “two-pronged” approach to develop the LCA guideline. The two prongs reflect the methodological implications of two types of goal definition: 1) studies conducted to aid product and process improvement, as well as for 2) communicating environmental performance results. Efforts in the coming years will be focused on harmonising the methodological approaches to defining the system boundary, functional and declared unit, impact assessment methods and indicators, data requirements and data quality assessment, product classification for vertical product-specific rules, and additional exploratory topics.

Table of contents

1 Scoping for the standardization and harmonization of LCA for pharmaceuticals.....	12
2 Scope of the harmonization process.....	16
2.1 Methods	16
2.2 Results and Discussion: Scope of PHARMECO LCA harmonisation	20
2.2.1 Purpose of the guidance	20
2.2.2 Goal definition.....	20
2.2.3 Comparative studies and comparative assertions	23
2.2.4 Interpretation of results	24
2.2.5 Geographical scope of the guidance.....	24
2.2.6 Reference standards and guidelines.....	24
2.2.7 Product scope.....	25
2.2.8 System boundaries	26
2.2.9 Impact assessment.....	28
2.2.10 Data and data quality.....	29
2.2.11 Structure of guidance.....	29
2.2.12 Exploratory topics	30
3 Summary and conclusion	32
4 References.....	33
5 Repository for primary data	36

List of Figures

Figure 1: PHARMECO implementation - overall works plan structure	13
--	----

Figure 2: Comparison matrix for goal and scope of existing method documents	15
Figure 3: Steps toward defining the scope for harmonisation	19
Figure 4: Methodological aspects with potentially differing requirements due to the two-pronged approach to the LCA guidance	22
Figure 5: Example cases for each of the goals for LCA studies of pharmaceutical products and processes.....	23
Figure 6: System boundaries for a simplified pharmaceutical product system	27
Figure 7: Rules for drug manufacturing processes, taken from Siegert et al. (2019).....	30

List of Tables

Table 1 PHARMECO datasets initial overview.....	11
Table 2: List of considered method documents, ordered by publication year	17
Table 3: Guiding questions for scoping workshops	18
Table 4: Summary of the scope of the two-pronged guidance document	32

Table 1 PHARMECO datasets initial overview

Data description	Data type	Data volume	Data origin	Data sharing
Work Package 8 - Standardization and harmonization of sustainability assessment systems				
General Documentation and reporting	.docx, .pptx, .xlsx., .pdf	< 1Gb	Created by WP8 based on partners contributions	Internal SharePoint until publication
Meeting slide decks and meeting minutes	.docx, .pptx, .xlsx., .pdf	< 1Gb	Created by WP8 based on partners contributions	Internal SharePoint
Mapped data from other tasks, educational material	.docx, .pptx, .xlsx., .pdf	<1Gb	Collected from partners in WP7	Internal SharePoint until publication

1 Scoping for the standardization and harmonization of LCA for pharmaceuticals

Despite also serving a public benefit, the continuously growing pharmaceutical and healthcare sectors are also a source of negative impacts on the environment (De Soete et al., 2017; Karliner et al., 2019; Siegert et al., 2020). The presence of active pharmaceutical ingredients (APIs) and their metabolites have been detected globally in environmental compartments such as soil and water (Umweltbundesamt, 2024). As bioactive substances, they have been linked to detrimental effects in ecosystems and pose a risk to biodiversity (Umweltbundesamt, 2025; Vidaurre et al., 2024). Besides pharmaceutical pollution, the healthcare sector and pharmaceutical industry are also significant contributors to climate change, representing around 4.4% of global greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions (Karliner et al., 2019). Emission of active pharmaceutical ingredients (APIs) into the environment may occur during drug development, production, use and post-use excretion, wash-off, and improper disposal (Siegert et al., 2020; Umweltbundesamt, 2025; Van Wilder et al., 2024).

Focusing efforts on the manufacture of small molecules, biologics, peptides and oligonucleotides, as well as on decontamination, PHARMECO aims to address the need to integrate more sustainable technologies and processes into pharmaceutical manufacturing. This is complementary to other EU projects such as ENKORE, which focus specifically on medical devices and packaging (Ötvös et al., 2025). PHARMECO is a collaboration between pharmaceutical and medtech companies, research institutions, government bodies and small and medium enterprises. As illustrated in *Figure 1* the core project comprises of three work packages on sustainable technology platforms, one work package on route design and one work package on pilot manufacturing, which are connected by a work package on sustainability assessment and steering (Ötvös et al., 2025). The work package on standardisation and harmonisation of sustainability assessment systems, (work package 8), aims to establish a harmonised and stakeholder-accepted methodological guideline applicable to (bio)pharmaceuticals. Through its engagement with the technical work packages along with that on sustainability assessment and steering, it has the advantage that methodological decisions can be road-tested, while in parallel analysing the environmental performance of the innovations explored within the technical work packages.

Figure 1: PHARMECO implementation - overall works plan structure

To steer the pharmaceutical industry towards more sustainable products and processes, associated (potential) environmental impacts must be determined to guide environmentally driven decisions throughout the pharmaceutical value chain. To do this, a common standard or harmonised guideline for the accounting of environmental impacts of pharmaceuticals is needed. Consistency in analyses is key to supporting environmentally driven product and process improvements and real impact reduction, so that insight may be gained into areas with high improvement potential, as well as ensuring that implemented measures and new technologies avoid burden shifting. Additionally, environmental metrics need to be communicated to support the evaluation of alternatives for procurement, policy and to meet regulatory and reporting requirements.

To date, a range of metrics have been developed to support the assessment of environmental performance of pharmaceuticals and pharmaceutical production. Mass-based green chemistry metrics are commonly used to assess the environmental performance of synthesis processes within the (fine) chemical sector. Metrics addressing environmental aspects, such as the Process Mass Intensity (PMI) and the Complete Environmental Factor (cEF) are efficiency-based and process-oriented, respectively representing ratios of the mass of raw materials, reactants and solvents required and the mass of wastes produced per specified mass of product (Kekessie et al., 2024). While these metrics have proved valuable when optimising the value and material efficiency of synthesis routes and processes, they are not without shortcomings. For instance, they do not account for material types, energy use, nor do they describe the (potential) impacts of these activities on the environment (De Soete et al., 2017; Jimenez-Gonzalez et al., 2011; Kekessie et al., 2024; Roschangar et al., 2022). Although the potential environmental impacts of efficiency improvements from waste or feedstock reductions could be inferred, and there have been correlations shown, for example between climate change and PMI (Jimenez-Gonzalez et al., 2011), the metrics themselves are limited to the scope of the analysed processes, and do not extend to the processes occurring in the preceding or subsequent value chain. Furthermore, as these metrics tend to focus on isolated segments of a pharmaceutical product’s life cycle – e.g. only certain synthesis steps within the process chain – they do not consider potential

burden shifting between processes, life cycle stages, or environmental impacts when an impact reduction measure is implemented (Moermond et al., 2025).

Today, with greater regulatory focus on pharmaceuticals in the environment, gaining visibility into hotspots and potential impacts occurring throughout a product's life cycle are of increasing importance. European regulatory developments such as the reform of the EU pharmaceutical legislation (European Commission, 2023b), as well as the Action Plan for the Chemicals Industry (European Commission, 2025) are increasingly focusing on a life cycle perspective and extended producer responsibility.

Life cycle assessment (LCA) has become a widely used method to assess the environmental impact of both products and processes, underpinning much of the EU's environmental policy around production and waste. It is a standardised method (ISO 14040/44:2006 for life cycle assessment) that enables the systematic analysis of the potential environmental impacts occurring throughout a product's life cycle, from raw materials extraction to its end-of-life (EoL) (International Organization for Standardization, 2006b). LCA can consider multiple environmental impacts occurring at different life cycle stages beyond merely the manufacturing of drug substances (DS) or drug products (DP). This allows for the identification of hotspots within the product life cycle, provides insight into potential burden shifting and, thereby, enables the evaluation of trade-offs between implemented "greener" measures (Siegert et al., 2019b).

Over the past few years, efforts toward methodological harmonisation for LCA in the pharmaceutical sector have increased, attempting to overcome the challenges posed by methodological inconsistency and incomparability among studies. This has culminated in a number of LCA and product carbon footprinting (PCF) guidelines and standards published by various stakeholder groups including by government health authorities, private-sector consortia, national standardisation bodies and academia. A non-comprehensive list of method documents was compiled by work package members and is shown in

Table 2: List of considered method documents, ordered by publication year, as a starting point for methodological discussions. Despite harmonisation efforts, key differences between these method documents remain. Some of the differences between them lie within the guidelines' goal and scope definition. These drive fundamental deviations in methodological decisions made when conducting LCA studies.

The differences among existing method documents are illustrated as a heatmap in *Figure 2*. Aspects of goal and scope definition with a high level of agreement among the analysed method documents are highlighted in green; those with some agreement but slight deviations between documents are highlighted in yellow, and aspects with little to no agreement between documents are highlighted in red. The documents are organised in order of publication date, with the most recent (2025) at the top, and the least recent (2011) at the bottom. The heatmap indicates increasing agreement in the method documents over time, however, there remain some aspects of the scope that lack harmonisation such as the key metrics for evaluating environmental sustainability performance, impacts and impact categories, consideration of health care pathways, functional unit, and handling of data gaps.

Elements of goal and scope definition

Method document

- Goal of assessment method
- Process/ Life cycle-oriented
- Geographic scope
- User of assessment method
- User of results / Audience
- Products in scope
- Key metrics of sustainability performance
- Impacts / impact categories included
- System boundaries
- Considers care pathways?
- Functional unit (if relevant)
- Intentional exclusions from scope
- Handling data gaps

Figure 2: Comparison matrix for goal and scope of existing method documents

In PHARMECO, work package 8 aims to facilitate the harmonisation process and establish an LCA guideline for (bio)pharmaceuticals that has been harmonised involving relevant stakeholders, including industry, research and regulatory institutions, both within and external to the PHARMECO Consortium. The guideline and its dissemination is the ultimate deliverable of the work package. This will be carried out by bringing relevant public and industry stakeholders together in a consensus-based harmonisation process, consisting of several rounds of discussions and workshops over five years. The methodological decisions will undergo road-testing using case studies within the project, to ensure applicability and robustness of the guideline.

This scoping document defines the topics for the harmonisation process for the LCA methodology and guideline that will be developed over the course of the PHARMECO project. It summarises the scoping decisions made following the consensus-based method outlined in section 2.1 and conducted in the first year of the PHARMECO project. This document outlines the aspects to include and exclude from the harmonisation process itself, and from the LCA guideline. To ensure consistency, uptake and usability of the guideline, as well as a harmonised scope for methodological decisions, it is key to involve relevant public and industry stakeholders from the initial scoping phase onwards, starting the harmonisation process with industry and public partners within the PHARMECO Consortium.

This deliverable is, therefore, the definition of a harmonised scope for the methodological harmonisation process and for the LCA guideline. The following sections outline the methods used for the harmonisation of the scope, followed by the results and discussion around the defined scope, and finally a conclusion and summary.

2 Scope of the harmonization process

2.1 Methods

The consensus-based harmonisation process for the scoping phase is illustrated in [Figure 3](#). The process was centred around a series of three structured workshops to achieve consensus on scoping decisions and included work package 8 members. Work package 8 consists of private and public partners, from research institutions and industry. The upcoming methodology harmonisation process will include insights and perspectives from key stakeholder groups, academia, industry, and regulatory institutions. The goal of each scoping workshop was to reach a consensus on methodological aspects to include or exclude from the scope of the harmonisation process and guidance.

The first step consisted of collecting a set of relevant method documents for an initial literature analysis. This analysis was used to identify gaps and challenges in current methods and acted as a basis for the scoping discussions in the workshops. The literature comprised of methodology documents related to environmental metrics and assessment methodologies relevant for the pharmaceutical industry, such as LCA and product carbon footprint (PCF) standards and guidelines, as well as scientific literature. The contribution and collection of literature to be considered in this process was open to all work package 8 members. The documents analysed are outlined in

[Table 2: List of considered method documents, ordered by publication year.](#)

Table 2: List of considered method documents, ordered by publication year

Document	Authors / Organisations	Year
PAS2090: Pharmaceutical products – Product category rules for environmental lifecycle assessments – Specification (draft, V1)	The British Standards Institution (BSI)	2025
Méthodologie d'évaluation de l'empreinte carbone des médicaments	EcovaMed / Ministry of the Economy, Finance and Industrial Sovereignty and Ministry of Health and Access to Care	2025
The Product Carbon Footprinting Guideline for the Chemical Industry: Specification for Product Carbon Footprint and Corporate Scope 3.1 Emission Accounting and Reporting (V3)	Together for Sustainability (TfS)	2024
Improved iGAL 2.0 Metric Empowers Pharmaceutical Scientists to Make Meaningful Contributions to United Nations Sustainable Development Goal 12	Roschangar et al.	2022
Product Category Rules (PCR) for pharmaceutical products and processes	Siegert et al.	2019
Challenges and recommendations for environmental sustainability assessments of pharmaceutical products in the healthcare sector	De Soete et al.	2017
Towards a holistic approach to metrics for the 21st century pharmaceutical industry	McElroy et al.	2015
Greenhouse Gas Accounting Sector Guidance for Pharmaceutical Products and Medical Devices	ERM / NHS Sustainable Development Unit	2012
Using the Right Green Yardstick: Why Process Mass Intensity is Used in the Pharmaceutical Industry to Drive More Sustainable Processes	Jimenez-Gonzalez et al.	2011

An evaluation matrix was constructed to analyse elements of the goal and scope considerations within the selected method documents and their methodological implications. As a key international standard for LCA, the ISO 14040/44:2006 were used as a reference to structure the analysis and matrix.

In the initial analysis, the method documents were dissected to compare their intended applications, users, audiences, geographic scope, impact assessment guidelines, product scope and function, formulation of functional and declared unit, system boundaries and considered processes, data-related requirements, and approaches to data gaps.

From the initial analysis, scoping questions were formulated, and these formed the backbone of the scoping workshops. The dissected method documents were drawn upon to support the discussions in the workshops. These examples provided insight into the potential implications of the explored methodological decisions, highlighting gaps and areas with high and low agreement between the method documents. This information was used to collectively decide whether there is added value in including the aspects into the scope of the PHARMECO harmonisation process. The scoping questions are listed in [Table 3](#).

In the workshops, the scoping questions were used as prompts for discussions. The discussions and decisions made were recorded in the meeting minutes. When high consensus was achieved on a scoping question this was considered a decision to include or exclude an aspect from the scope.

Questions which yielded low consensus on topics to include or exclude were taken forward into the following workshop for further discussion until consensus was reached.

Topics covered in the first workshop included the goal of an LCA study in the pharmaceutical sector, the product scope and function, impact assessment, definition of the system boundaries and included processes, structure of the guidance document, and gaps and challenges identified in the literature. The second workshop was used to discuss open topics, which had low or no consensus in the first workshop, to further refine the scope. These included the geographical scope of the guideline, the definition for pharmaceutical product in scope, data quality and requirements, reference standards and methodological baseline. The results of the first two workshops – aspects with the highest consensus – were subsequently drafted into a scoping document. This document was circulated to work package members and other relevant PHARMECO stakeholders for commenting. The third workshop was subsequently held as the final workshop to achieve final consensus on the scope for harmonisation, embodied by this scoping document.

The process followed to achieve the harmonised scope definition is outlined in [Figure 3](#).

Table 3: Guiding questions for scoping workshops

Topic	Guiding questions
Goal of sustainability assessment	What is the intended application of the sustainability assessment results within PHARMECO? Who is the target audience? e.g. Internal use for process/product improvements/research? External communication to policymakers? Communication to procurers of chemical precursors/drug substance/drug product?
	Should the guideline be focused on Europe or globally applicable?
	Should the guideline support comparative assertions? (i.e. environmental claim regarding the superiority or equivalence of one product versus a competing product that performs the same function [ISO14044:2006 definition 3.6])
Impact assessment	Do we want to focus only on environmental impacts, or also social and economic?
	Which impact categories should be included? Is this the same for all products/processes in PHARMECO scope, or would there need to be some adjustment?
	Do we want to consider / add flexibility for emerging topics, which are not yet covered by our available impact methods and characterisation models? (e.g. antimicrobial resistance, nanotoxicity)
Products and function	How do we define the object of study for the guideline? (e.g. product, process, organisation, care pathway?)
	Do we want to use the Directive 2001/83/EC definition for “medicinal product” to define our objects of study?
	Do we want to include diagnostic drugs/substances in scope?
	Which elements should be included when defining the functional unit? (e.g. how to define the function, which patient information is important to include, location of administration)
System boundaries	What should be included within the system boundaries? What are we excluding?

Data quality and requirements	Do we want to include sections on how to approach data gaps, data quality evaluation, and requirements for primary and secondary data?
Structure and basis of guideline	Do we want to work towards a horizontal (sectoral) guideline that supports further product-specific approaches?
	Reference standards: Which existing standards do we want to consider core standards? Which ones do we consider supporting standards?
	Is there the inclination to selecting a “main” seed document, to base the PHARMECO guideline on?
Exploratory topics	Considering circularity
	Considering non-attributable processes
	Considering coverage of some diagnosis products
	Considering social and economic impacts.

Figure 3: Steps toward defining the scope for harmonisation

2.2 Results and Discussion: Scope of PHARMECO LCA harmonisation

The following section outlines the scope for methodology harmonisation and of the PHARMECO LCA guideline. The results represent the decisions made during the scoping workshops and are essential for defining and structuring the methodological harmonisation phase. This section outlines the results (scoping decisions) and reasoning behind them, discussed by the participants of this scoping phase.

2.2.1 Purpose of the guidance

With several LCA method development and standardisation projects currently ongoing for the pharmaceutical and health sectors, it is important to evaluate the purpose and intended audience of the PHARMECO guidance document. Although there was wide agreement that the pharmaceutical industry would be a key user of the guidance document, topics around further relevant users and the ultimate dissemination format (e.g. formal standard, industry guidelines) and uptake of the guidance are still to be explored. This will form part of the scope for discussions in the upcoming methodology harmonisation phase, as further methodological guidance documents and standards – such as the PAS 2090 (BSI, 2025) are published. As an initial step in the next phase of the project, a stakeholder analysis and engagement plan will be developed, to identify and engage with key stakeholders with high interest and stakes, to include them in the harmonisation process.

These discussions will enable the contextualisation of the PHARMECO guidance in the ecosystem of active projects and stakeholders striving for similar goals.

2.2.2 Goal definition

The goal definition in LCA is a fundamental step, as this determines the purpose of an LCA study and thereby contributes to forming the scope of analysis and many of the methodological decisions, including the system boundaries, the functional unit formulation, data (quality) requirements, the impacts evaluated, and the interpretation of results. During the scoping workshops, the discussions around goal definition were centred around the intended application of studies, the target audiences, and the necessity of comparative assertions.

To support goal definition, drivers for conducting LCA studies in the pharmaceutical industry were explored during the workshops and used to identify their intended applications. The discussed drivers have been summarised and clustered, as follows:

1. *Market access*: There is pressure on industry from clients or vendors, as well as audiences who are external to the pharmaceutical value chain to provide information on environmental performance of pharmaceutical products. These actors include national medicines agencies, public health authorities, and institutions that provide healthcare and related services, such as insurance companies. This pressure is also linked to regulatory developments, such as client requests for product carbon footprints (PCF), as part of their scope 3 greenhouse gas (GHG) accounting and binding net zero targets, making external communication and reporting a priority, also from a business standpoint.
2. *Regulatory developments*: Currently, reporting requirements – such as disclosing corporate scope 3 GHG emissions – are enabled by LCA. Based on recent developments such as the

reform of the EU pharmaceuticals regulation (European Commission, 2023b), which also places an emphasis on pharmaceuticals in the environment, requirements for reporting may become more stringent and require more specific data.

3. *Customer requests*: Companies report receiving customer requests for environmental data on their products and processes. The need to respond to customer requests also suggests the need to build capacity and resources to calculate, record, and report this data.
4. *Market differentiation*: Underlining differences in the environmental profile of products and alternatives is considered a competitive advantage. Comparability needs consistent guidelines and data quality to establish a level playing field.
5. *Product improvement*: Industry is required to demonstrate improvements in the environmental performance of products, and to provide an improvement pathway, in addition to meeting decarbonisation goals and commitments. LCA studies support in both designing an improvement pathway and providing environmental metrics to communicate the improvement.

A common thread throughout the five listed drivers is the need to communicate LCA results to third parties. This is also reflected in most of the analysed LCA-based method documents, as their intended application is to generate results to communicate and report (BSI, 2025; EcovaMed, 2025; Penny et al., 2012; Siegert et al., 2019a). Also recurring is the need to demonstrate and meet environmental impact reduction commitments. These two use-cases for implementing LCA in the industry lead to the decision to pursue a “two-pronged” guideline, intended to accommodate different purposes and audiences, yet remain consistent with each other:

1. **Goal 1**: Improvement of products & processes driven by decisions aimed to minimise environmental impacts. The intended audience of these studies are internal actors, such as those responsible for process design and improvements, third-party suppliers, as well as research and development.
2. **Goal 2**: Communication of environmental performance to inform procurement and policy decisions and meet reporting requirements. The intended audience of these studies are generally external actors, such as other actors in the pharmaceutical value chain, and policy and public (health) authorities.

The two-pronged approach means that the guidelines will provide methodological support for studies carried out with the two goals defined above. The need for distinction between the two types of use cases was underlined, as each use case may lead to different methodological decisions, including the defined system boundaries, data granularity and data quality, LCIA impact categories and methods, functional units. *Figure 4* is a conceptual figure, illustrating the potentially differing methodological decisions required by a study conducted under goal 1 compared to that conducted under goal 2, *Figure 5* provides a set of (non-comprehensive) example cases for each goal. Designing a two-pronged guidance aims to avoid methodological compromise between requirements for a reporting guideline and one for internal product and process improvements, as well as mitigate the risk of companies using conflicting guidelines.

Figure 4: Methodological aspects with potentially differing requirements due to the two-pronged approach to the LCA guidance

Figure 5: Example cases for each of the goals for LCA studies of pharmaceutical products and processes

2.2.3 Comparative studies and comparative assertions

An additional requirement highlighted by industry is the comparison of alternatives and competitor products. It was underlined in the workshops that comparative studies are important for both manufacturers and procuring organisations to support the selection of products and processes, based on environmental performance.

The resulting scoping decision concluded that there should be guidance provided on conducting comparative studies, however, that no additional guidance was necessary for comparative assertions. For comparative assertions, the requirements outlined in the ISO 14044 apply and can be referred to.

2.2.4 Interpretation of results

Guidance on interpretation of results includes identifying what information can be derived from analysis of the LCA findings based on the goal of the study. It also provides guidance on how to evaluate a study's consistency, completeness, and sensitivity to modelling decisions, to determine its robustness.

Due to the two-prong approach to the guideline, it is important to distinguish between results that can be derived for communication, and those that can be derived for improvement purposes, along with the minimum requirements for consistency, completeness, and sensitivity.

2.2.5 Geographical scope of the guidance

Pharmaceutical companies have global entities and complex value chains. To avoid regional differences in the way LCAs of pharmaceuticals are conducted, and additional administrative burden, a global guidance was opted for, to enable consistency between studies carried out in different regions, and support transferability of LCA data throughout international supply chains. This scope is intended to also encourage uptake by practitioners operating in geographically diverse locations, including suppliers and customers.

To implement this geographical scope, the guidance must also accommodate methodological considerations which may differ between geographical locations. Examples include the use of life cycle impact assessment (LCIA) methods which have characterisation factors with sufficient coverage of diverse regions, approaches to the issue of data availability or gaps, and alignment with global standards.

The scoping decision is to provide guidance on how to consider different geographic regions, but not to provide specific guidance on requirements for all possible locations. The guidance will not go beyond what is already required in the ISO 14044.

2.2.6 Reference standards and guidelines

The decision to align on a core standard from the beginning of the harmonisation process is important to ensure compliance of the resulting analyses to a specific standard and its requirements. Supporting standards provide useful references for methodological aspects and their requirements.

Due to global geographical scope, the guideline will be based on key international standards. The core standards identified for compliance are the ISO 14040/44:2006 standards on LCA and supplemented by the ISO 14020 series on environmental statements and programmes for products, specifically the ISO 14025:2006 on type III environmental declarations and the ISO 14026:2017 on principles, requirements and guidelines for communication of footprint information. Guidelines for communication of LCA results will also be aligned with the ISO 14020 series, including guidelines on types of critical review, and documentation.

In 2025, at the time of writing, the British Standards Institute (BSI) were in the process of developing a draft Publicly Available Specification (PAS), the PAS 2090 standard, which specifies product category rules for reporting the environmental LCA results of pharmaceutical products (BSI, 2025). This has been selected to be used as a supporting standard as well as a baseline document to inform the development of the two-pronged PHARMECO LCA guideline, particularly for the communication prong.

Additional supporting standards and guidelines identified are the Together for Sustainability (TfS) initiative's Product Carbon Footprinting Guideline for the Chemical Industry: Specification for Product Carbon Footprint and Corporate Scope 3.1 Emission Accounting and Reporting (Version 3), the European Commission's Product Environmental Footprint, and the Greenhouse Gas Protocol Product Standard. These documents are widely used in industry and will inform the methodological harmonisation process for the PHARMECO guideline. This list of supporting standards and guidelines may still evolve over the course of the project.

2.2.7 Product scope

In LCA, the product system and respective impacts are described relative to the functional unit and reference flow. Therefore, the product and product's function are essential aspects to define. A central consideration when defining the product scope includes whether the product systems are comparable to a degree that the same set of rules may be applied to conduct LCA, or whether a different set of rules may be necessary. This is further elaborated in section 2.2.10, pertaining to establishing product categories, and section 2.2.11.4 for vastly differing products, or objects of study.

Similar to the existing LCA and PCF guidelines for the pharmaceutical sector outlined in

Table 2: List of considered method documents, ordered by publication year

Table 2: List of considered method documents, ordered by publication year, the definition of pharmaceutical product will follow that of the European Medicines Agency (EMA), which is aligned with the European Commission's Directive 2001/83/EC:

Medicinal product: *“A substance or combination of substances that is intended to treat, prevent or diagnose a disease, or to restore, correct or modify physiological functions by exerting a pharmacological, immunological or metabolic action.”* (European Medicines Agency, 2025c)

Although most guidelines base their product scope on the definition laid out in Directive 2001/83/EC, they tailor the definition to include a sub-set of products falling under the listed functions of the pharmaceutical products in Part B of the definition. It is interesting to note that the two guidelines analysed that were published on behalf of national health authority guidelines - *Méthodologie d'évaluation de l'empreinte carbone des médicaments* by ECOVAMED for the Ministry of the Economy, Finance and Industrial Sovereignty and Ministry of Health and Access to Care (2025) and the *Greenhouse Gas Accounting Sector Guidance for Pharmaceutical Products and Medical Devices* by ERM for the UK's National Health Service Sustainable Development Unit (2012) – both use the full product scope and function listed in the legal definition of a pharmaceutical product in Directive 2001/83/EC. However, it is important to note that these guidelines do not include additional guidance on conducting studies of diagnostics products, although they fall within scope.

The scoping decision made on the product scope for the PHARMECO LCA guideline was to include both pharmaceutical products (e.g. drug substances, drug products) and processes (e.g. manufacturing processes, decontamination). Based on the two-pronged guidance, and the two goals for analysis, it was deemed important to consider both products and processes as objects of study, to ensure sufficient visibility and granularity into the studied system to enable process and product optimisations, as well as to cover reporting requirements; Environmental optimisation of a decontamination or manufacturing process may come with a different set of requirements than for optimising an entire DP, for instance (Emara et al., 2018). Therefore, the applicability and methodological implications of having a product or process as the object of study will be explored, such as the potentially different functionality of the object of study.

It was also decided to limit the product scope to human pharmaceuticals, explicitly excluding veterinary pharmaceuticals. The exclusion of veterinary pharmaceuticals was decided due to the differences that arise in the product system from the use phase to the EoL stage. Among these differences are the waste treatment processes that occur and points of entry to environmental compartments. Veterinary pharmaceuticals therefore require a separate methodological guideline.

Process studies can be conducted, for instance, when the focus of the study follows [Goal 1](#) and is aimed at improvement or process optimisation based on environmental indicators. A process study might employ a mass-based declared unit and will possibly have a gate-to-gate or cradle-to-gate system boundary. As the intended audience is internal and aimed at actors responsible for process optimisation, the analysis should enable integration into existing pharmaceutical development processes but also needs to be compatible with product-level studies.

Excluded from scope are care pathways as a standalone object of study. Instead, these will be considered in the analyses as part of the use-phase considerations for pharmaceutical products. The scoping discussions around the topic of care pathway inclusion concluded that the crux of the care pathway is the attributability of processes to the function of the pharmaceutical product. The scope of analysis for a care pathway is much broader than for a pharmaceutical product, consisting of additional processes such as diagnosis, testing, logistics, and social aspects. Therefore, it requires a separate guidance document.

Also excluded are standalone medical devices, which will also be included in the use-phase of pharmaceutical products if they are required for administration to patients.

A separate section in the guidance on conducting the LCA of diagnostics products has also been excluded from scope. This is predominantly due to the fact that they do not fall within the project scope of PHARMECO and will not be able to undergo the same road-testing as the other pharmaceutical products within scope, leading to potential inconsistencies or blind spots. However, it was agreed that although some diagnostics agents – such as radiopharmaceuticals – have vastly different process chains to biologics and synthetics, others may be similar enough to apply the PHARMECO LCA guideline. A separate evaluation will be conducted at a later stage in the methodological harmonisation process.

2.2.8 System boundaries

The definition of the system boundary is highly dependent on the goal of the study and the functional unit. To date, guidance on this is still relatively inconsistent between existing method documents for the sector. Obtaining harmonised rules for establishing system boundaries is key when striving for consistency and comparability within and between studies. The system boundaries drawn determine

what processes are included in the analysed system, and, thereby, where insight can be obtained into environmental hotspots and visibility into potential burden shifting. Moreover, the definition of the system boundaries also affects the rules and requirements for the use of primary and secondary data, as well as for modelling processes and pathways that lie out of the company's control, such as those in the use and EoL stages.

Error! Reference source not found. shows a simplified pharmaceutical product system and three different system boundaries: cradle-to-gate, gate-to-gate, and cradle-to-grave. Cradle-to-gate describes life cycle stages from the raw materials acquisition to the packaged product at factory gate. Depending on the perspective of the LCA practitioner from where they are in the pharmaceutical value chain, this product could be, for instance, a drug substance or drug product). The gate-to-gate boundary encompasses only the processes occurring during manufacture. The cradle-to-grave boundary includes all the life cycle stages that the finished product undergoes, including downstream transportation and distribution, use, and end-of-life (excretion, wash-off, and/or disposal).

Figure 6: System boundaries for a simplified pharmaceutical product system

There was broad consensus during the scoping discussions that a full life cycle should be considered for product studies, and that an exploration of system boundary setting should be included within the scope for methodology harmonisation. Within the scope for the harmonisation process is also the investigation of implications of setting different system boundaries for objects of study (i.e. products and processes). Additionally, there was also consensus that guidance should be provided on carrying out cradle-to-gate studies used for process studies, or requests from customers for cradle-to-gate environmental footprint data.

Specific cut-off rules will be determined during the methodological harmonisation phase and included in the scope of the LCA guideline, along with key assumptions and modelling requirements for the core system. This includes the use-phase and EoL stage. Allocation rules for multifunctional processes will also be defined in the methodological harmonisation phase and will be included in the scope of the guideline. Furthermore, guidance on modelling processes such as waste-to-energy and material recycling, along with approaches to recycled and biogenic content will be included. Excluded from scope for the time being are clinical trials, quality assurance (QA) and quality control (QC) processes, due to attributability issues. There was agreement that these processes should be studied in isolation rather than be attributed to a product.

Industry has stressed that following EU regulatory developments such as the reform of the Pharmaceutical Regulation (European Commission, 2023b) and their increased focus on extended producer responsibility in underlying Directives, more in-depth analysis and reporting on

pharmaceuticals emissions into the environment – also at EoL – may be required in the near future. At the same time, approaches to modelling the use and EoL stages are also largely inconsistent among the method documents. The differing approaches and assumptions are partly due to visibility issues and LCI data gaps in these life cycle phases (Emara et al., 2019; Satta et al., 2024). The method documents propose different modelling assumptions and recommendations, and at differing levels of detail. Examples are consideration of fate in the human body after administration, assumptions regarding (ir)regular disposal scenarios of products, wastewater treatment, and approaches to EoL allocation (BSI, 2025; Penny et al., 2012; Siegert et al., 2019a). Therefore, it was widely agreed among the work package members that use of pharmaceutical products (including exploration of how to consider fate in the human body) and modelling of EoL should be included within scope for the methodological harmonisation phase.

2.2.9 Impact assessment

LCA is a multi-impact method, and the selection of meaningful impact categories is essential to avoid burden-shifting. There was also wide consensus among participants that more impact categories would support a more holistic picture of the product system's potential environmental impacts, especially important for product improvement. The selection of LCIA methods and impact categories (indicators) are also largely driven by goal and product under study, as not all impacts may be relevant for the full spectrum of pharmaceutical products that fall in the guideline's scope. Other factors such as geographical coverage of characterisation factors in LCIA methods are also relevant to consider. Therefore, the identification of relevant impact categories and explore how they can be determined was included in scope for the methodology harmonisation phase.

Although the decision on specific indicators and methods will be decided during the methodology harmonisation phase of the PHARMECO project, there was already broad consensus to base LCIA in the guideline on a full scope of midpoint indicators. Arguments mentioned for using midpoint indicators include the difficulty of implementing end-point indicators for business decisions, as well as compatibility with other guidelines. On the other hand, end-point indicators may be useful for mid- to end-point contribution analyses, in supporting the identification of important midpoints. Endpoint indicators as part of the communication prong of the guidance was also discussed by participants. The resulting conclusion, however, was that current reporting requirements tend to demand midpoint indicators, and they are more tangible to derive actions from, for the time being.

Indicators for reporting may also be influenced by regulatory developments and resulting market demands. Developments such as upcoming EU regulation – e.g. the revised Urban Wastewater Directive – and increased focus on biobased feedstocks were mentioned to underline the need to also consider indicators beyond only climate change, such as ecotoxicity and land-use, despite there being uncertainty and fundamental gaps in their methods. Moreover, with growing attention to impacts such as antimicrobial resistance and nanotoxicity, it should also be explored if and how impacts that are not yet covered by existing LCIA methods could be considered. This is therefore included in scope as an exploratory topic.

For reporting, on the other hand, a sub-set of indicators may be required, which will be defined in the methodological harmonisation phase. The indicators themselves have not yet been selected, however, the need for internal consistency within LCIA methods arose as a core topic, particularly when methods are to be applied to a global geographical scope.

Excluded from the initial scope are social and economic indicators. This decision may be re-evaluated at a later stage.

2.2.10 Data and data quality

Data and data quality requirements are essential to include within the scope of the guideline to be compliant with the ISO 14044. Guidance on these aspects would support consistency and comparability between studies. During the workshops, industry identified the need to have an established set of data requirements to aid interoperability of data transferred throughout the supply chain. Industry also suggested that a widely adopted data guideline for LCA in pharmaceuticals could support efforts aimed at further developing the capabilities of supply chain actors with currently less mature data. This would enable a level playing field in terms of data consistency and quality within the industry and throughout the value chain. Moreover, it was suggested that a set of data rules may encourage and improve the willingness to share data throughout the supply chain, due to the effect of the level playing field.

Although the data requirements themselves will be defined during methodological harmonisation process, there scoping decisions were made concerning which elements of data and data quality requirements should be included in the harmonisation process and resulting guidance document. The requirements will be outlined for both [Goal 1](#) and [Goal 2](#), and must be consistent for each prong of the guidance. It will be explored how, and whether, a hierarchy of requirements can be defined between these two types of study supported by the guidance. Elements within scope include approaching data gaps on, for instance, missing precursor production and raw materials, regional datasets, fate in the human body and at EoL, unused products, missing toxicity data and impact pathways in the environment. Furthermore, requirements for primary and secondary data use, including decision support will be in scope. Separately, requirements and guidance on the use of proxy data will be provided. Data quality evaluation methods and documentation requirements will also be defined in the methodological harmonisation phase, along with the data implications concerned with the two-pronged guidance.

2.2.11 Structure of guidance

Although the LCA guideline would be a sectoral guideline, a topic that was discussed was whether these “horizontal” sector-wide rules should also be supplemented with a set of “vertical” specific rules for product categories. An example is shown in [Figure 7](#), where the authors define generic rules for conducting LCA for pharmaceutical products, and define vertical rules for product categories defined by their therapeutic function (Siegert et al., 2019b). Here, a trade-off may need to be navigated between comparability and specificity of the rules; a horizontal guidance may be more conducive to comparability between studies, but may compromise on specificity, for instance.

Figure 7: Rules for drug manufacturing processes, taken from Siegert et al. (2019b).

Of general interest to the project stakeholders was to consider developing interfaces in the horizontal sectoral guidance to accommodate vertical guidelines. It was therefore decided to consider both a horizontal and vertical guidelines to be within the scope of harmonisation.

A challenge was discussed, however, on how to define the product categories for the vertical guidance documents. Ideas were proposed, such as classification by therapeutic area, delineation between biologics and synthetics, large and small molecules, and representative products. These ideas and their implications will be explored in methodological harmonisation phase of the project.

2.2.12 Exploratory topics

During the scoping workshops, a few topics emerged that appeared to both be gaps in the method documents and topics of methodological interest to the work package members, or of potential relevance to the PHARMECO project scope. These topics were circularity, coverage of social and economic impacts, and consideration of diagnostics products and care pathways.

The listed topics were those with little consensus regarding inclusion within the scope of the guideline, but with high interest among the project partners to include as exploratory topics, from a methodological standpoint. These exploratory topics will be included in scope for the methodological harmonisation process for re-evaluation of their relevance for the scope of the guideline, in a later phase of the project.

2.2.12.1 Circularity

Circularity has, in recent years, also emerged as a topic of interest in the healthcare and pharmaceutical industries, some circularity initiatives were highlighted in the European Federation of Pharmaceutical Industries and Associations' (EFPIA) White Paper on Circular Economy (EFPIA, 2024). With circularity measures already being implemented within industry, there is a high interest in also evaluating the associated sustainability improvements associated with these measures.

Although falling within the scope of the PHARMECO project within work package 7 on sustainability assessment and steering, it remains to be determined to what extent circularity considerations could be included into the scope of the LCA guideline.

There was high consensus on the need to provide guidance on how to consider and model circularity measures in pharmaceutical product systems. Methodological options for modelling current circular practices in the pharmaceutical industry will be explored. This will also be partly informed by the work carried out on circularity assessment methods for pharmaceutical products in work package 7. Explicitly excluded from scope was the integration of a circularity indicator in the LCA guideline.

2.2.12.2 Non-attributable processes

Within some existing method documents, several non-product-specific processes have been identified as being “non-attributable”, yet it has been acknowledged that they are important to consider due to their higher impact contributions and the sensitivity of the processes (BSI, 2025; Siegert et al., 2019a). Method development is, therefore, required to enable the consistent attribution of these more generic processes to the product system under study.

Among these processes are storage, cleaning-in-place (CIP), sterilisation-in-place (SIP), and heating, ventilation and air conditioning (HVAC). The level of detail provided in the method documents to date on how to attribute these non-attributable processes to the product system vary significantly. Some documents merely mention the exclusion of cleaning and/or sterilisation without providing a dedicated guidance on how to allocate the process inputs and emissions to the product itself (Penny et al., 2012; Siegert et al., 2019a). Others, suggest allocation by Stock Keeping Unit (EcovaMed, 2025), or by economic or physical allocation depending on the product and its properties (BSI, 2025).

Due to the high sensitivity of these processes in pharmaceutical LCA studies, as well as their high impact contribution, there was consensus that there should be further exploration of these methods and guidance on how to include them into the system boundaries. Furthermore, establishing how to delineate between non-attributable processes to exclude and those to include will also be explored, and whether these may be applicable to previously excluded processes such as QA and QC.

2.2.12.3 Social and economic impacts

Pharmaceutical products are designed to have a societal benefit. With LCA studies in the sector predominantly focused on the environmental pillar of sustainability, the social and economic impacts and benefits resulting from these product systems are much less explored. With the surge of ESG reporting and of the policy landscape further developing towards increasing supply chain visibility, with new regulation such as the EU’s Corporate Sustainability Due Diligence Directive, companies are increasingly required to turn their attention also to social impacts occurring within their supply chains. Social life cycle assessment (SLCA) has been put forward as an assessment method to account for impacts, and authors Debaveye et al., (2020) propose also combining a so-called handprint method in parallel with LCA, to also account for the human health benefit of pharmaceuticals via end-point impact assessment methods.

Within PHARMECO’s work package 7 on sustainability assessment and steering, work on these methods will be conducted. In the scoping workshops, there was consensus reached that these would be initially set out of scope of the LCA guideline, but that a scoping iteration at a later stage of the methodological harmonisation phase could be used to evaluate the potential integration into scope based on the developments in work package 7.

2.2.12.4 Diagnostic products and care pathways

As described in section 2.2.4, diagnostic products and care pathways were excluded from scope as standalone objects of study. A main reason for this is that the product systems differ significantly when compared to the process chains associated with the manufacture use, and EoL of biologics and synthetics. Furthermore, diagnostic products and care pathways do not fall under the PHARMECO scope of manufacturing innovations. As these will be used to test methodological decisions at a later stage of the project, products not falling within scope will not be able to undergo the same road-testing, leading to inconsistencies.

Although there was wide consensus to exclude both as standalone objects of study, the systems will be re-evaluated and mapped during the methodological harmonisation phase, to determine to what extent the defined methodological decisions can be applied to diagnosis products and care pathways.

3 Summary and conclusion

The decisions made during the scoping process determine the scope of the LCA methodological harmonisation process and ultimately of the PHARMECO LCA guideline. The scoping decisions for aspects to include within the upcoming methodology harmonisation phase are summarised in [Table 4](#). This next phase will culminate in draft guidelines for road testing using case studies. As the harmonisation process is interactive and iterative, the scope and methodological decisions will be revisited throughout the project. Further input and expertise from relevant stakeholders, not currently in the work package or in PHARMECO will also be drawn on.

Contrary to the other method documents analysed, PHARMECO stakeholders identified two main goals for conducting LCA studies in the pharmaceutical sector: product and process improvement and communication and reporting. This has been a determining factor in establishing the scope of the harmonisation exercise and of the guideline, as the two goals each come with different implications with regard to methodological requirements. Defining two goals attempts to avoid methodological compromise between requirements yet maintain consistency between the two prongs of the guideline. Over the course of the methodology harmonisation phase, efforts will be focused on harmonising the decisions to define the system boundary, functional and declared unit, impact assessment methods and indicators, data requirements and data quality assessment, product classification for vertical product-specific rules, and additional exploratory topics. The PHARMECO guideline aims to contribute valuable road-tested methodological improvements, as well as address a gap in the published method documents to date – namely, to develop a methodological guideline that supports not only the communication of environmental impact results but also assists in achieving product and process improvements.

Table 4: Summary of the scope of methodology harmonisation for the two-pronged guidance document

Scope	Goal 1	Goal 2
Goal definition	Product and process improvement	Communication and reporting
Audience	Internal; Actors responsible for process design and improvements	External; Policymakers, procurement bodies, other value chain actors
System boundaries	Potentially gate-to-gate, cradle-to-gate, cradle-to-grave	Potentially cradle-to-gate, cradle-to-grave

Product scope	Processes and products	Products
Definition pharmaceutical product	Based on EMA and Directive 2001/83/EC definition but excluding diagnostics.	
Functional unit	Functional unit used for product studies Declared unit may be used for process studies	Functional unit used for product studies Declared unit may be used
Core standards	ISO 14040/44:2006	ISO 14040/44:2006 ISO 14025:2006 ISO 14026:2017 PAS 2090
Supporting standards	Together for Sustainability (TfS) initiative's Product Carbon Footprinting Guideline for the Chemical Industry: Specification for Product Carbon Footprint and Corporate Scope 3.1 Emission Accounting and Reporting (V3) The European Commission's Product Environmental Footprint The Greenhouse Gas Protocol Product Standard	
Impact assessment	Comprehensive set of mid-point indicators	Depending on communication purpose, either comprehensive or sub-set of midpoint indicators
Data requirements	Granularity and use of primary, secondary, and proxy data should be conducive to improvements	Granularity and use of primary, secondary, and proxy data should meet communication and reporting requirements
	Compatibility of data requirements between Goal 1 and Goal 2 assessments	
	Guidance on approaching data gaps (data gaps may differ in significance based on the purpose of study)	
Data quality assessment	Guidance on data quality evaluation methods and data quality rating Documentation requirements	
Geographical scope of guideline	Globally applicable	
Guideline structure	Horizontal sectoral guidance document, with interfaces to develop product-specific vertical rules	
Exploratory elements	Consideration of circularity within systems	
	Consideration of "non-attributable" processes	
	Consideration of diagnostics drugs and care pathways	
	Inclusion of social and economic aspects	

4 References

- BSI, 2025. PAS 2090 Pharmaceutical products – Product category rules for environmental lifecycle assessments – Specification [WWW Document]. Stand. Dev. URL <https://standardsdevelopment.bsigroup.com/projects/9025-12045> (accessed 6.13.25).
- De Soete, W., Jiménez-González, C., Dahlin, P., Dewulf, J., 2017. Challenges and recommendations for environmental sustainability assessments of pharmaceutical products in the healthcare sector. *Green Chem.* 19, 3493–3509. <https://doi.org/10.1039/C7GC00833C>
- Debaveye, S., De Smedt, D., Heirman, B., Kavanagh, S., Dewulf, J., 2020. Quantifying the handprint—Footprint balance into a single score: The example of pharmaceuticals. *PLOS ONE* 15, e0229235. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0229235>
- EcovaMed, 2025. Carbon Footprint of Medicines: Assessment Methodology.

- Emara, Y., Lehmann, A., Siegert, M.-W., Finkbeiner, M., 2019. Modeling pharmaceutical emissions and their toxicity-related effects in life cycle assessment (LCA): A review. *Integr. Environ. Assess. Manag.* 15, 6–18. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ieam.4100>
- Emara, Y., Siegert, M.-W., Lehmann, A., Finkbeiner, M., 2018. Life Cycle Management in the Pharmaceutical Industry Using an Applicable and Robust LCA-Based Environmental Sustainability Assessment Approach, in: Benetto, E., Gericke, K., Guiton, M. (Eds.), *Designing Sustainable Technologies, Products and Policies*. Springer International Publishing, Cham, pp. 79–88. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-66981-6_9
- European Commission, 2025. A European Chemicals Industry Action Plan (Communication) COM(2025) 530.
- European Commission, 2023a. Proposal for a Directive of the Council on the Union code relating to medicinal products for human use, and repealing Directive 2001/83/EC and Directive 2009/35/EC (Communication) COM(2023) 192.
- European Commission, 2023b. Proposal for a reform Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council laying down Union procedures for the authorisation and supervision of medicinal products for human use and establishing rules governing the European Medicines Agency, amending Regulation (EC) No 1394/2007 and Regulation (EU) No 536/2014 and repealing Regulation (EC) No 726/2004, Regulation (EC) No 141/2000 and Regulation (EC) No 1901/2006 (Communication) COM(2023) 193.
- European Commission, 2013a. What you Need to Know about Biosimilar Medicinal Products (Consensus Information Paper 2).
- European Commission, 2013b. Commission Recommendation of 9 April 2013 on the use of common methods to measure and communicate the life cycle environmental performance of products and organisations (2013/179/EU). *Off. J. Eur. Union* L124, 1–210.
- European Medicines Agency, 2025a. EudraGMDP Glossary [WWW Document]. EudraGMDP. URL https://eudragmdp.ema.europa.eu/help_public/content/v3_0_user_manual/glossary.htm (accessed 10.5.25).
- European Medicines Agency, 2025b. Glossary - Regulatory terms: Excipient [WWW Document]. URL <https://www.ema.europa.eu/en/glossary-terms/excipient> (accessed 10.28.25).
- European Medicines Agency, 2025c. Medicinal product [WWW Document]. URL <https://www.ema.europa.eu/en/glossary-terms/medicinal-product> (accessed 9.21.25).
- European Medicines Agency, 2000. Good Manufacturing Practice for Active Pharmaceutical Ingredients (CPMP/ICH/4106/00).
- International Organization for Standardization, 2018. ISO 14067:2018: Greenhouse gases - Carbon footprint of products - Requirements and guidelines for quantification.
- International Organization for Standardization, 2017. ISO/TS 14027:2017: Environmental labels and declarations - Development of product category rules.
- International Organization for Standardization, 2015. ISO 14001:2015: Environmental management systems - Requirements with guidance for use.
- International Organization for Standardization, 2006a. ISO 14040:2006: Environmental management - Life cycle assessment - Principles and framework.
- International Organization for Standardization, 2006b. ISO 14044:2006: Environmental management - Life cycle assessment - Requirements and guidelines.
- Jimenez-Gonzalez, C., Ponder, C.S., Broxterman, Q.B., Manley, J.B., 2011. Using the Right Green Yardstick: Why Process Mass Intensity Is Used in the Pharmaceutical Industry To Drive More Sustainable Processes. *Org. Process Res. Dev.* 15, 912–917. <https://doi.org/10.1021/op200097d>
- Karliner, J., Slotterback, S., Boyd, R., Ashby, B., Steele, K., 2019. Health Care's Climate Footprint.

- Kekessie, I., Wegner, K., Martinez, I., Kopach, M.E., White, T.D., Tom, J.K., Kenworthy, M.N., Gallou, F., Lopez, J., Koenig, S.G., Payne, P.R., Eissler, S., Arumugam, B., Li, C., Mukherjee, S., Isidro-Llobet, A., Ludemann-Hombourger, O., Richardson, P., Kittelmann, J., Sejer Pedersen, D., Van Den Bos, L.J., 2024. Process Mass Intensity (PMI): A Holistic Analysis of Current Peptide Manufacturing Processes Informs Sustainability in Peptide Synthesis. *J. Org. Chem.* 89, 4261–4282. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.joc.3c01494>
- Moermond, C.T.A., Puhlmann, N., Pieters, L., Matharu, A., Boone, L., Dobbelaere, M., Proquin, H., Kümmerer, K., Ragas, A.M.J., Vidaurre, R., Venhuis, B., De Smedt, D., 2025. Eco-pharma dilemma: Navigating environmental sustainability trade-offs within the lifecycle of pharmaceuticals – A comment. *Sustain. Chem. Pharm.* 43, 101893. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scp.2024.101893>
- Ötvös, S.B., Verstappen, B., Baillon, B., Kappe, C.O., Weigelt, D., Luu, D., Brutin, F., Welsh, H., Dewulf, J., Caous, J., Colberg, J., Boone, L., Finkbeiner, M., Müllenborn, M., Schipper, N., Petronis, S., Hawdon, S., Fernandes, S.M., Braje, W.M., Mackintosh, W., De Soete, W., Bayon, Y., Schönau, C., Costers, S., 2025. Advancing Safe and Sustainable by Design Practices in Pharmaceutical Manufacturing: The PHARMECO Project. *ChemSusChem* e202501218. <https://doi.org/10.1002/cssc.202501218>
- Penny, T., Fisher, K., Collins, M., Allison, C., 2012. Greenhouse Gas Accounting Sector Guidance for Pharmaceutical Products and Medical Devices.
- Roschangar, F., Li, J., Zhou, Y., Aelterman, W., Borovika, A., Colberg, J., Dickson, D.P., Gallou, F., Hayler, J.D., Koenig, S.G., Kopach, M.E., Kosjek, B., Leahy, D.K., O'Brien, E., Smith, A.G., Henry, M., Cook, J., Sheldon, R.A., 2022. Improved iGAL 2.0 Metric Empowers Pharmaceutical Scientists to Make Meaningful Contributions to United Nations Sustainable Development Goal 12. *ACS Sustain. Chem. Eng.* 10, 5148–5162. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acssuschemeng.1c01940>
- Satta, M., Passarini, F., Cespi, D., Ciacci, L., 2024. Advantages and drawbacks of life cycle assessment application to the pharmaceuticals: a short critical literature review. *Environ. Sci. Pollut. Res.* <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11356-024-33964-w>
- Siegert, M.-W., Finkbeiner, M., Emara, Y., Lehmann, A., 2019a. Product Category Rules (PCR) for pharmaceutical products and processes. <https://doi.org/10.14279/DEPOSITONCE-9143>
- Siegert, M.-W., Lehmann, A., Emara, Y., Finkbeiner, M., 2019b. Harmonized rules for future LCAs on pharmaceutical products and processes. *Int. J. Life Cycle Assess.* 24, 1040–1057. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11367-018-1549-2>
- Siegert, M.-W., Saling, P., Mielke, P., Czechmann, C., Emara, Y., Finkbeiner, M., 2020. Cradle-to-grave life cycle assessment of an ibuprofen analgesic. *Sustain. Chem. Pharm.* 18, 100329. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scp.2020.100329>
- Umweltbundesamt, 2025. Entry, occurrence, and effects of pharmaceuticals in the environment [WWW Document]. URL <https://www.umweltbundesamt.de/en/entry-occurrence-effects-of-pharmaceuticals-in-the#undefined> (accessed 9.17.25).
- Umweltbundesamt, 2024. The UBA database – “Pharmaceuticals in the environment” [WWW Document]. URL <https://www.umweltbundesamt.de/en/database-pharmaceuticals-in-the-environment-0#the-database> (accessed 9.17.25).
- Van Wilder, L., Boone, L., Ragas, A., Moermond, C., Pieters, L., Rechlin, A., Vidaurre, R., De Smedt, D., Dewulf, J., 2024. A holistic framework for integrated sustainability assessment of pharmaceuticals. *J. Clean. Prod.* 467, 142978. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2024.142978>
- Vidaurre, R., Bramke, I., Puhlmann, N., Owen, S.F., Angst, D., Moermond, C., Venhuis, B., Lombardo, A., Kümmerer, K., Sikanen, T., Ryan, J., Häner, A., Janer, G., Roggo, S., Perkins, A.N., 2024. Design of greener drugs: aligning parameters in pharmaceutical R&D and drivers for environmental impact. *Drug Discov. Today* 29, 104022. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.drudis.2024.104022>

5 Repository for primary data

DATA SUMMARY	
Dataset reference	Meeting minutes: Scoping workshop #1
Reference Work Package / Deliverable	WP8 D8.1
Data Manager	TUB
Date of update of the dataset table	06/10/2025
Specific Metadata	Scoping decisions, minutes, WP8
Description and purpose	Documentation of scoping discussions and decisions made within scoping workshops. These decisions define the scope for harmonisation and are compiled in this scoping document.
Data origin	Meeting minutes
Data Size	1.38 MB
Availability	Restricted to the consortium
Accessibility	Authentication for PHARMECO SharePoint with username and password and two-factor authentication
Standards	General adherence to GDPR ruling and to the project consortium signed agreement (CA).
PID (Persistent Identifier of the dataset) or identification of the storage repository	WP8 – Standardization and harmonization/03_Organisation/02_Meetings/WP 7+8 F2F Brussels – May 2025 WP 7+8 F2F Brussels - May 2025
Does the data underpin a publication	No
PID (Persistent Identifier of the publication)	n/a
Is the meta data accessible through open access?	No
Data format	docx
Software tool	Microsoft Office
Utility & Re-use	PHARMECO Consortium (specifically WP2,7,8,9)

Archiving and preservation (storage/backup)	Backup storage on TUB servers.
Ethical aspects	None

DATA SUMMARY	
Dataset reference	Meeting minutes: Scoping workshop #2
Reference Work Package / Deliverable	WP8 D8.1
Data Manager	TUB
Date of update of the dataset table	06/10/2025
Specific Metadata	Scoping decisions, minutes, WP8
Description and purpose	Documentation of scoping discussions and decisions made within scoping workshops. These decisions define the scope for harmonisation and are compiled in this scoping document.
Data origin	Meeting minutes
Data Size	460 KB
Availability	Restricted to the consortium
Accessibility	Authentication for PHARMECO SharePoint with username and password and two-factor authentication.
Standards	General adherence to GDPR ruling and to the project consortium signed agreement (CA).
PID (Persistent Identifier of the dataset) or identification of the storage repository	WP8 – Standardization and harmonization/03_Organisation/02_Meetings 20250617_WP8_Scoping_Workshop_2_Minutes.docx
Does the data underpin a publication	No
PID (Persistent Identifier of the publication)	n/a
Is the meta data accessible through open access?	No
Data format	docx
Software tool	Microsoft Office

Utility & Re-use	PHARMECO Consortium (specifically WP2,7,8,9)
Archiving and preservation (storage/backup)	Backup storage on TUB servers.
Ethical aspects	None

DATA SUMMARY	
Dataset reference	Meeting minutes: Scoping workshop #3
Reference Work Package / Deliverable	WP8 D8.1
Data Manager	TUB
Date of update of the dataset table	06/10/2025
Specific Metadata	Scoping decisions, minutes, WP8
Description and purpose	Documentation of scoping discussions and decisions made within scoping workshops. These decisions define the scope for harmonisation and are compiled in this scoping document.
Data origin	Meeting minutes
Data Size	665 KB
Availability	Restricted to the consortium
Accessibility	Authentication for PHARMECO SharePoint with username and password and two-factor authentication.
Standards	General adherence to GDPR ruling and to the project consortium signed agreement (CA).
PID (Persistent Identifier of the dataset) or identification of the storage repository	WP8 – Standardization and harmonization/03_Organisation/02_Meetings/WP 7+8 F2F Berlin – September 2025 WP 7+8 F2F Berlin - September 2025
Does the data underpin a publication	No
PID (Persistent Identifier of the publication)	n/a
Is the meta data accessible through open access?	No

Data format	docx
Software tool	Microsoft Office
Utility & Re-use	PHARMECO Consortium (specifically WP2,7,8,9)
Archiving and preservation (storage/backup)	Backup storage on TUB servers.
Ethical aspects	None